

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING THE PHYTON PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE IN DIFFERENT FIELDS

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Abstract. *In this article, the use of Python programming language in various fields, its positive aspects and some disadvantages are analyzed.*

Keywords: *programming languages, Python, C++ programming language, Global Interpreter Lock, Version Compatibility.*

Introduction. Although the Python programming language does not have a long history, its development is currently one of the most promising fields. The Python programming language was developed in the late 80s of the last century [1]. Unlike other programming languages, the Python programming language is designed to perfection. The Python programming language provides independent control of other software tools and their components. In fact, Python can be learned as a multi-purpose programming language, which allows you to program a number of processes. The Python programming language, unlike other programming languages, has the ability to create several types of programs at the same time, i.e.: - allows creating practical, web-based, scientific software products [2,3]. Python has no limits on memory usage and performance requirements, meaning the possibilities are so vast that it does not have a data declaration layer like other programming languages. Such opportunities, of course, serve to dramatically increase the efficiency of the work of program creators [4,5].

Features of the Python programming language. Python is one of the few modern programming languages that is easy to learn and at the same time powerful. Python provides high-level data structures and simple but efficient object-oriented programming techniques [6]. Unique features of Python:

- Simple, easy-to-learn, easy-to-start programming, free and open-source software with simple syntax;
- It is not necessary to take into account lower-level details, for example, memory management, while writing the program;
- Can work on many platforms without any modifications;
- Language to be interpreted;
- Expandable language. If we want the program to work somewhere faster, we can write this part in C or C++ programming languages and then run (call) this part through python code [7,8,9];

- It has a lot of different libraries;
- work with xml/html files;
- working with http requests;
- GUI (graphical interface);
- Creation of websites;
- Working with FTP;
- Work with picture audio video files;
- In robotics;
- Mathematical and scientific computing programming.

Python can be used in large projects. Because it has no limits, its potential is high. It is also the best among programming languages due to its simplicity and universality. Nowadays, there are companies working with Python in various fields. For example, companies such as Google, NASA, and Dropbox write their programs in Python [10].

Disadvantages of Python programming language.

1. Performance: Compared to lower level languages like C or C++, Python can be slower in terms of execution speed. Python is an interpreted language, which means it may not be as efficient as compiled languages. However, Python's performance is sufficient for most applications, and using specialized libraries can help mitigate performance issues.
2. Global Interpreter Lock (GIL): Python has Global Interpreter Lock (GIL). Thus, even on multi-core systems, only one thread can execute Python bytecode at the same time. This limits the performance of multithreaded applications that are tied to the CPU. However, Python offers alternatives such as multiprocessing and asynchronous programming with libraries such as asyncio to bypass the GIL limitation.
3. Mobile and Browser Support: Python is not widely used in mobile app development compared to languages like Swift (for iOS) or Kotlin (for Android). While there are frameworks like Kivy and BeeWare that allow you to develop mobile apps using Python, the ecosystem is not as mature as native development languages.
4. Memory consumption: Python's memory consumption can be higher than some other programming languages due to dynamic typing and automatic memory management. This can be a problem with large applications or systems with limited memory resources.
5. Version Compatibility: There are several major versions of Python and backward compatibility between different versions can sometimes be difficult. For example, porting code from Python 2 to Python 3 may require adjustments

due to language and library differences. However, with Python 3 support officially ending on January 2, 2020, it is recommended that you adopt Python 3.

Despite these drawbacks, Python's extensive libraries, ease of use, and readability make it a popular choice for a wide variety of applications [11,12,13]. These include web development, data analysis, scientific computing and machine learning. However, it is important to consider the specific requirements of the project and evaluate how Python meets them [14,15].

Analysis of results

If you are just starting to learn programming, Python programming language is a very good choice for you. One of the main features of the Python programming language is its simplicity, which in turn makes it a great option for those just learning programming. Most programs written in the Python programming language are very short compared to other programming languages such as C or C++. This brevity makes it possible to have fewer errors in the program and reduce the time it takes to prepare a project. We can use this programming language to create computer programs, create applications that work with databases, write programming for networks and write games. Python is a cross-platform programming language, which allows you to easily write code on Windows, MacOS, and Linux.

Conclusion. As a result of our analysis, we can say that the Python programming language is known as one of the most popular languages in the world today. It is a programming language that is bright, easy, and has a clear syntax with a fairly high level of convenience. Python can be used in several fields: web programming, data analysis, work automation and other fields. There are three main areas in which the Python programming language can be used on a large scale: web programming (writing applications for the backend-webserver), artificial intelligence problems, and small tasks that the user does a lot on the computer (sending e-mails, printing, searching and printing files, extracting some data from a spreadsheet, etc.).

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